

Incommensurate skyrmionic phase in triangular spin lattice of helimagnet NiBr₂

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Abstract

The spin-spiral magnets are an important class of multifunctional material that shows coupling between ferroelectric polarization magnetic orders. The triangular-lattice of antiferromagnetic nickel dibromide (NiBr₂) with helical spin structures often exhibits a highly unusual magnetic ordering due to competition between ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic exchange interactions. Using DC (AC) magnetometry, a detailed investigation of incommensurate skyrmionic phase at low temperature has been carried out. In such helix phase ($T < T_H = 23\text{K}$) the elliptically disordered spins successfully detected. The strength of disorder can control by varying the temperature as assured by kink shaped magnetic hysteresis loops measured in helix phase ($T < T_H$). These experimental findings are highly significant for the proper understanding of the involved microscopic mechanisms in the precursor stage of incommensurate skyrmions, which has various technological implications for next-generation magnetic memory devices.

Keywords: Helimagnetism, Skyrmion, domain wall, Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction.

References

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